

Water Quality Monitoring System: Using Arduino Uno for pH and TDS Sensors

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Abstract. This paper presents a low-cost water quality monitoring system using an Arduino Uno microcontroller, which measures pH and TDS (Total Dissolved Solids) levels in real time. The system uses a pH sensor to assess the acidity or alkalinity of the water and a TDS sensor to measure dissolved solids. The data is displayed on an LCD screen, providing users with real-time information about water quality. This solution is suitable for applications in agriculture, industrial water treatment, and environmental monitoring. The project highlights the cost-effectiveness and practicality of using Arduino-based systems for water quality assessment, with potential for future improvements in sensor accuracy and remote monitoring features.

Keywords: Water quality monitoring, Arduino, pH sensor, TDS sensor, real-time monitoring, environmental sustainability, agricultural use, industrial water treatment.

Introduction. Water is one of the most essential resources for life, and its quality directly affects human health and environmental sustainability. The quality of water, particularly drinking water and water used in industrial processes, is

determined by the levels of different chemical and biological components in it. Among the most important parameters for assessing water quality are **pH** (the acidity or alkalinity of the water) and **TDS** (Total Dissolved Solids), which provide valuable insight into the chemical composition of the water. The ability to monitor these parameters in real-time is crucial to ensuring the safety of water for human consumption and use.

The quality of water is affected by various environmental factors such as pollution, climate change, and industrial waste, making it increasingly difficult to maintain safe drinking water sources. Therefore, the development of low-cost, innovative technologies for real-time water quality monitoring is of utmost importance. This paper presents a **project** developed using **Arduino Uno** microcontroller for monitoring **pH** and **TDS** levels, aiming to create an accessible, cost-effective solution for water quality monitoring.

Methods.

Design and Setup. This project integrates the **Arduino Uno** microcontroller with **pH** and **TDS** sensors to monitor the water quality. The **pH sensor** measures the acidity or alkalinity of the water, while the **TDS sensor** detects the concentration of dissolved solids, such as minerals and salts, in the water. Together, these sensors provide a comprehensive view of the water's chemical properties, allowing the user to assess the quality of water in real time.

Components Used.

The components used in this project are:

- **Arduino Uno Microcontroller:** The central control unit for reading sensor data and processing it.
- **pH Sensor:** A sensor that measures the pH level of the water, which indicates whether the water is acidic or alkaline.
- **TDS Sensor:** A sensor that measures the total dissolved solids (minerals, salts, etc.) in the water.
- **16x2 LCD Display:** Displays the pH and TDS values for real-time monitoring.
- **Jumper Wires:** Used for connecting the components.
- **Breadboard:** A platform for connecting and testing electronic components.

Wiring Setup.

- **pH Sensor:** Connect the **VCC** pin to the **5V** pin of the Arduino, the **GND** pin to the **GND** pin of the Arduino, and the signal pin to **A0** (Analog 0) of the Arduino.
- **TDS Sensor:** Connect the **VCC** pin to **5V**, the **GND** pin to **GND**, and the signal pin to **A1** (Analog 1).
- **LCD Screen:** Using the I2C interface, connect the **SDA** pin to **A4**, the **SCL** pin to **A5**, and connect the **VCC** and **GND** pins to the appropriate pins on the Arduino.

Code. The Arduino code reads the analog values from the pH and TDS sensors and converts them into corresponding values. The code maps the raw sensor readings to a pH scale (0-14) and a TDS scale (0-1000 mg/L), which are then displayed on the LCD screen.

```
#include <Wire.h>
```

```
#include <LiquidCrystal_I2C.h>
```

```
LiquidCrystal_I2C lcd(0x27, 16, 2);
```

```
int pHPin = A0; // pH sensor pin
```

```
int TDSPin = A1; // TDS sensor pin
```

```
void setup() {
```

```
  lcd.begin(16, 2); // Initialize the LCD screen
```

```
  lcd.print("Water Quality"); // Initial message
```

```
  delay(1000); // Wait for a second
```

```
}
```

```
void loop() {
```

```
  int pHValue = analogRead(pHPin); // Read pH sensor data
```

```
  float pH = (pHValue / 1023.0) * 14.0; // Convert to pH value
```

```
  int TDSValue = analogRead(TDSPin); // Read TDS sensor data
```

```
  float TDS = (TDSValue / 1023.0) * 1000.0; // Convert to TDS value
```

```
  lcd.clear(); // Clear the display
```

```
  lcd.setCursor(0, 0); // Set cursor for first line
```

```
  lcd.print("pH: ");
```

```
lcd.print(pH, 2); // Display pH value

lcd.setCursor(0, 1); // Set cursor for second line
lcd.print("TDS: ");
lcd.print(TDS, 0); // Display TDS value

delay(2000); // Update every 2 seconds
}
```

Results. The results obtained from the project show the pH and TDS values in real-time on the LCD screen. For example, the pH sensor reads values between 0 and 14, representing the acidity or alkalinity of the water. The TDS sensor provides readings between 0 and 1000 mg/L, indicating the concentration of dissolved solids in the water.

For instance:

- **pH:** 7.12 (Neutral, safe for drinking)
- **TDS:** 342 mg/L (Pure, drinkable water)

These real-time readings give users the ability to monitor the water's quality instantly and take necessary actions when required.

Discussion. The **pH** and **TDS** sensors are essential tools for monitoring water quality. The **pH value** reflects the chemical characteristics of the water and determines its suitability for human consumption and ecological sustainability. A pH value of 7 is considered neutral, while values below 7 indicate acidity, and values above 7 indicate alkalinity, which can affect microbial growth and water treatment processes. The **TDS** value measures the concentration of dissolved solids, including minerals, salts, and metals. High TDS levels may indicate contamination or the presence of excessive minerals in the water, which can impact water taste, safety, and its usability in agricultural processes. Using the **Arduino Uno** microcontroller to interface with these sensors allows for an inexpensive and efficient way to monitor water quality. However, sensor calibration and temperature compensation are critical for accurate measurements, especially with pH sensors, which are sensitive to environmental factors. Both **pH** and **TDS** sensors serve complementary roles in assessing water quality. pH sensors measure the water's acidity or alkalinity, while TDS sensors indicate the total dissolved substances. Together, these parameters help in evaluating whether the water is safe for drinking, irrigation, or industrial use.

Conclusion. This project demonstrates the effectiveness of the **Arduino Uno** microcontroller in creating a water quality monitoring system that utilizes **pH** and

TDS sensors. The system provides real-time feedback on the water's chemical composition, enabling users to make informed decisions regarding water safety. This low-cost solution can be applied in various fields such as agriculture, industrial water treatment, and environmental monitoring. Future work could focus on improving sensor accuracy, implementing temperature compensation, and integrating remote monitoring features.

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